

AN ANALYTICAL EVALUATION OF INTERFACIAL BONDING PROPERTIES OF SINGLE/MULTI-WALLED NANOTUBE/POLYMER COMPOSITES.

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ABSTRACT

Since the discovery of carbon nanotubes, extensive research in the use of the nanotubes as nano-reinforcements for advanced composite materials has been dramatically emerged. The nanotubes have been appreciated as revolutionary high strength materials with possessing many unique electrical, mechanical and thermal properties in the World. The high aspect ratio property of the nanotubes enable them to be used as nano-fibres and nano-conductors for improving the electrical and thermal conductivity, and delamination resistance and fracture properties of polymer-based composite structures. To adopt these nano-materials in real structural applications, understanding their stress transfer properties between the nanotubes and surrounding matrices is a prior and important issue. In this paper, the stress transfer properties between single-/multi-walled nanotubes and polymer matrix are theoretically studied through the uses of local density approximation, elastic shells and conventional fibre pullout models. Several parameters such as the wall thickness, Young's modulus, volume fraction and chiral vectors of the nanotubes were considered in the study. According to the analytical results, it was found that the maximum shear stress decreases with increasing the size of the nanotubes. Increasing the number of wall layers of the nanotubes will cause (1) the decrease of the Young's modulus and (2) the increase of the effective cross section area of the nanotubes and thus the increase of the total surface contact area at the bond interface. Although the author has previously addressed that multi-walled nanotubes (MWNTs) could not be effectively used as nano-reinforcements for nanotube/polymer composites due to the axial stress could not be continuously transferred from the surface layer to the inner shells, the use of the MWNTs may have an advantage of avoiding debonding at the bond interface between the nanotubes and matrix of the composites. Besides, the stress transfer length of zigzag (n,0) nanotube is comparatively shorter than that of the armchair (n,n) and chiral (n,m) nanotubes where $m \neq 0$. In some cases, the Young's modulus of the MWNTs is high enough for the design of advanced nanotube/polymer composites even their modulus is comparatively smaller than that of the single-walled nanotubes (SWNTs).

Keywords: Carbon nanotubes; Interfacial properties; Nanocomposites.

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INTRODUCTION

The history of carbon nanotubes could be traced back to the discovery of the fullerence structure C₆₀ (buckyball) in 1985 [1]. The structure of the buckyball comprises of 60 carbon atoms arranged by 20 hexagonal and 12 pentagonal faces to form a spherical structure, when the buckyball is constantly elongated to form a long and narrow tube with a diameter of approximately one to several nms (10Å), which is the basic form of a carbon nanotube (it will be simply called a "nanotube" in the rest of this

paper). In 1991, a Japanese electron microscopist Iijima [2] has discovered fullerene-related structures, which consist of multi-graphene cylinders closed at either end with caps containing pentagonal rings with outer diameters of 4-30 nm by a direct-current arc discharge between carbon electrodes immersed in helium gas under a temperature of 3000°C, the multi-walled nanotubes (MWNTs) were created. Until recent years, single-walled nanotubes (SWNTs) as smaller as 0.4 nm in diameter have been made [3], and such small SWNTs raise new possibilities for electrical superconductivity that could have a great impact as the critical temperature for superconductivity becomes higher [4]. Structurally, the shape of the SWNTs could be imagined that a graphene sheet rolls into a tubule form with end seamless caps together with very high aspect ratios of 1000 or more [5]. As individual molecules, the SWNT is believed to be a mostly defect-free structure leading a high strength despite their low density [6]. In Fig.1, the shapes of nanotubes are shown by a schematic illustration and a scanning electron microscopy (SEM) image. The diameter of the nanotubes showed in the image is about 70 nm.

Figure 1. The schematic illustration (left) and scanning electron microscopy (right) images of the nanotubes.

Apart from their inherent structural and electronic properties, the MWNTs could also be used as frictionless nano-actuators for the development of nano-motors, nano-bearings and nano-springs in general NEMs technologies [7]. Dresselhaus et al. [8], Mintmire and White [9] and Lau and Hui [10] have provided comprehensive reviews on the physics, structural and mechanical properties, and applications of the nanotubes, respectively. In the past few years, many researches have focused on the mechanical properties of nanotube/polymer composite structures. MWNTs were randomly buried into polymer-based materials to form advanced composites [11-12]. It has been recognised that high mechanical strength could be achieved when all the nanotubes are aligned parallel to the load direction in the composite structures.

In order to introduce these advanced nano-structural elements for real-life applications, the connectivity with, and uniform distribution within the matrix are essential structural requirements for building up ultra-strong nanotube composites. A good interfacial bonding characteristic allows all stresses could be transferred alternatively between the matrix and nanotubes. Although many previous works have addressed that the nanotubes possess superior strength properties, the exact stresses, which are borne by these high strength nanotubes are unknown because of the uncertainty in the bonding between the nanotubes and surrounding matrix. Bower et al [13] have concluded that the load transfer from polymer to nanotube was not sufficient to fracture the nanotubes. The failure of nanotube/polymer composite appeared to arise from pullout of the nanotubes and from mechanical fracture of the polymer matrix. Wagner et al. [14] have also addressed the interfacial shear stress is affected by the size and modulus of the nanotubes. They conducted the fragmentation tests of nanotube/polymer composite films to determine their interfacial bonding strength between the

nanotube and matrix. Liao and Li [15] have recently determined that the maximum interfacial shear stress where a nanotube was pulled-out of a nanotube/polymer system was about 160 MPa by using molecular dynamic simulation. It has been proved that there is no chemical bonding between nanotubes and some polymer-based materials [16]. In the absence of atomic bonding properties, the adhesion between the nanotube and polymer consists of electrostatic and van der Waals interaction, and stress arising from the mismatch in coefficient of thermal expansion of materials. Wagner [17] and Cooper et al. [18] have found that the average shear stress between the nanotubes and polymer matrix is correlated to the embedded length of the nanotubes. They indirectly conducted the nanotube pullout test of a nanotube/polymer composite film and the whole pullout process was observed under the transmission electron microscopy (TEM). The maximum shear strength of 376 MPa was measured. Raman spectroscopy is an effective tool to study the interfacial bonding characteristic of nanotubes related composite structures. Fig.2 shows the Raman spectrum for composites with different nanotube weight fractions.

Figure 2. Raman spectra of nanotube/polystyrene composites with different nanotube fractions

In this study, the interfacial bonding and stress transfer properties between the nanotubes and matrix are theoretically studied by using the well-developed local density approximation model [19], classical elastic shell theory [20] and conventional fibre pullout model developed by Zhou et al.[21]. Several parameters such as the wall thickness, Young's modulus, volume fraction and chiral vectors of the nanotubes were considered in the study. It has been reported that the classical elastic theories could be used to study the stress transfer and deformation of nanotube-based structures [22-24].

THEORETICAL APPROACH

In the past, most analytical studies used a constant Young's modulus E_{NT} to study the mechanical properties of nanotubes and nanotube/polymer composites. However, many experimental works have proved that the modulus of MWNTs was less than that of a single-walled structure. Tu and Ou-Yang [20] have used the local density approximation model cooperated with an elastic shell theory to estimate the Young's modulus of MWNTs structures. They found that the Young's modulus of the nanotubes decreases with increasing the numbers of wall layers N . The Young's modulus E_{SWNT} , Poisson ratio ν_{NT} and effective wall thickness h of the SWNT used in their study were 4.7 TPa, 0.34 and 0.75 Å, respectively. The radius of the first layer (an inner layer) of nanotubes could be determined by using the rolling graphene model:

$$\rho_o = \frac{\sqrt{m^2 + n^2 + mn}}{\pi} \sqrt{3a_o} \quad (1)$$

where ρ_o , m , n and a_o are the non-relaxed radius and indices of the SWNTs and C-C bond distance (1.42\AA), respectively. The Young's modulus E_{NT} of MWNTs estimated by using the local density approximation model and classical elastic shell theory can be expressed as [20]:

$$E_{NT} = \frac{N}{N-1+R} E_{SWNT} R \quad (2)$$

where R denotes the thickness to spacing ratio of the nanotubes (h/d). It is obvious that for $N=1$, the $E_{NT} = E_{SWNT}$, which corresponds to the result of the SWNT. The parameter d is the spacing between each graphene layer ($\approx 3.4\text{\AA}$). The outer radius of the MWNTs could be determined by $R_{NT} = \rho_o + d(N-1)$. In Fig. 1a the construction of an MWNT/polymer composite is shown. The MWNT could be imagined as a group of co-axial circular shells packed together with a uniform interval spacing d and the effective wall thickness h . The effective cross sectional area of the nanotubes can be calculated by

Figure 3. Schematic diagrams of the nanotube/polymer composites (a) and simple fibre pullout model (b).

$$A_{eff} = 2\pi h \left\{ N\rho_o + \sum_{C=1}^N d(C-1) \right\} \quad (3)$$

Since the role of the nanotubes in advanced composite structures is to take up all stresses that are transferred from the matrix through the interfacial shear stress, their bonding properties between the nanotubes and matrix should be studied in detail. A well-known classical fibre pullout model was used to study the interfacial bonding problem of nanotube/polymer composites. Three-dimensional, axisymmetric cylinder model was proposed to study the stress transfer behaviours between the nanotubes and matrix. The mechanical properties and geometrical factors that were used in the present study were followed by the data given in [20] and Eqs. (1) and (2). In Fig.1a, the analytical fibre pullout model is shown. The interfacial shear stress occurs when a nanotube is subjected to a pullout force, which is generated by a crack opening, propagating perpendicularly to the longitudinal axis of the nanotubes.

The nanotube with an outer radius of R_{NT} is located at the centre of a coaxial cylinder matrix with an outer radius of b . The total embedding length of the nanotube is L . Assuming that the nanotube is undertaking a pullout force, F due to the existence of crack opening and the bonding force on the other end cap of the nanotube is very small, thus the axial stress applied on the other end where $z = L$ is equal to zero. The boundary conditions at two ends of this model are:

$$\sigma_{NT}^z(0) = \sigma_{pullout} \quad , \quad \sigma_{NT}^z(L) = 0 \quad (4a, b)$$

$$\sigma_m^z(0) = 0 \quad , \quad \sigma_m^z(L) = \gamma \sigma_{pullout} \quad (5a, b)$$

where σ represents the stress, the superscripts denote the coordinates of the three principal axes (r , θ , z) and subscripts 'NT' and 'm' refer to the materials of the nanotube and matrix, respectively as indicated Fig.1b. γ is the area ratio of the nanotube and matrix, i.e.

$$\gamma = \frac{R_{NT}^2}{b^2 - R_{NT}^2} \quad (6)$$

The pullout stress, $\sigma_{pullout}$ can be determined by F/A_{eff} . The equilibrium between the axial stress of the nanotube and interfacial shear stress $\tau(z)$ in the nanotube's longitudinal direction can be expressed as [25-26]:

$$\frac{d\sigma_{NT}^z(z)}{dz} = -\frac{2}{R_{NT}} \tau(z) \quad (7)$$

$$\frac{d\sigma_m^z(z)}{dz} = \frac{2\gamma}{a} \tau(z) \quad (8)$$

By considering the boundary conditions given by Lau et al. [25], Gao et al. [27] and Zhou [28], the general equilibrium equations for a 3-D axisymmetric problem [29] and the continuity of axial and radial deformations at the any bonded interfaces, the axial stress in the nanotubes can be written as a following differential equation form:

$$\frac{d\sigma_{NT}^z(z)}{dz} - A_1 \sigma_{NT}^z(z) - A_2 \sigma_{pullout} = 0 \quad (9)$$

By using the boundary conditions at two nanotube's ends as indicated in Eqs (4) and (5), and considering the relationship in Eq.(7), the equations of the nanotube's axial and the interfacial shear stresses can be obtained as:

$$\sigma_{NT}^z(z) = \omega_1 \sinh(\lambda z) + \omega_2 \cosh(\lambda z) - \frac{A_2}{A_1} \sigma_{pullout} \quad (10)$$

and

$$\tau(z) = \frac{-R_{NT}\lambda}{2} [\omega_1 \cosh(\lambda z) + \omega_2 \sinh(\lambda z)]. \quad (11)$$

The parameters of A_1 , A_2 , λ , w_1 , w_2 are the functions of the mechanical properties and geometrical factors of the nanotube and matrix, and are listed in an appendix I.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

For a simple fibre pullout model, the maximum interfacial shear stress is located at a pullout end region where $z = 0$. The magnitude of the shear stress is highly affected by the inherent properties and geometrical factors of the nanotubes and matrices. In the present study, the total embedding length of the nanotubes and the outer diameter of the cylinder were $10 \mu\text{m}$ and $4 \mu\text{m}$, respectively. The Young's modulus and Poisson's ratio of the matrix (epoxy) were 3.3 GPa and 0.48 , respectively [30]. A pullout force of 1 nN is applied to the end of the nanotubes. In Fig.4, it is clearly seen that the maximum shear stress of an SWNT/epoxy composite is comparatively higher than that of other composites made by MWNTs subjected to the same pullout force. The decreases of the maximum shear stress of MWNTs composites may be due to the decrease of the nanotubes' modulus so as the modulus ratio of the nanotube to the matrix (E_{NT}/E_m). Another reason may be due to the reduction of an axial stress in the nanotubes because of the increase of the effective cross sectional area of the MWNTs. However, this equation fails to correct for the shear stress dropping to zero when $z = L$. The analytical results also indicate that the decrease of the interfacial shear stress is not linear proportional to the volume fraction of the nanotubes so as the surface contact area. The figure shows that the increase the amount of nanotubes could eventually reduce the load taken by each individual nanotube. Therefore, the interfacial bonding strength between the nanotube and matrix is reduced.

Figure 4. Plot of the interfacial shear stress against the embedding length of SWNT and MWNTs.

In Fig.5, a plot of the interfacial shear stress of SWNTs with different chiralities is shown. In the figure, it shows that the maximum shear stress of a zigzag nanotube is comparatively higher than that of chiral (5,3) and armchair (5,5) nanotubes. Because of the small cross sectional area of the zigzag nanotubes as determined by Eq.(1), the total surface contact area at the bond interface of the zigzag nanotube is therefore comparatively smaller than that of the others, and hence, higher the interface shear stress is resulted. Although it is shown in the figure that the maximum shear stresses of the chiral and armchair nanotubes are lower compared with the zigzag nanotubes, they are required a long stress transfer length to allow all stresses to be fully transferred from the matrix to the nanotubes. Therefore, according to the trend of the curves shown in the figure, the maximum shear stress at the interface of the nanotube is not only affected by the Young's modulus but also the cross sectional area of the nanotubes.

Figure 5. Plot of the interfacial shear stress against the embedding length of different chiral nanotubes

It is well known that the maximum shear stress should be located at the starting point of the bond where $z = 0$, it therefore the allowable pullout force (P_{cr}) and the tension stress (σ_{cr}^*) in the nanotube/polymer system could be estimated by rearranging Eq.(11) once the allowable interfacial shear stress (τ_{max}) is known by using the following equations:

$$P_{Cr} = \frac{2\tau_{max} \sinh(\lambda L)}{R_{NT} \lambda A_{eff} \left(\frac{A_2}{A_1} - \left(1 + \frac{A_2}{A_1} \right) \cosh(\lambda L) \right)} \quad (12)$$

and

$$\sigma_{cr}^* = \frac{P_{cr}}{A_{eff}} \nu_{NT} + \sigma_m^* (1 - \nu_{NT}) \quad (13)$$

where ν_{NT} and σ_m^* denote the volume fraction of the nanotubes and the stress in the matrix at the nanotube stress is equal to P_{cr}/A_{eff} . Liao and Li [15] have recently determined the maximum interfacial shear stress where a nanotube was pulled out, of a nanotube/polymer system is about 160 MPa by using molecular simulation. By substituting this value into the Eq.(12), it is possible to determine the maximum nanotube pullout force of the system. The results show that the allowable pullout force of the nanotubes increases with increasing the number of the wall layer, thus decreasing the interfacial shear stress between the nanotubes (MWNTs) and matrix. This trend is satisfied to the experimental

results addressed in literature [31]. The increases the number of layers and embedding length of nanotubes would results in decreasing the induced shear stress at the bond interface. Both factors are significant in the design of the use of nanotube/polymer composites

CONCLUDING REMARKS

The interfacial bonding characterisation of nanotube/polymer composites was analytically studied. In the study, it was found that the decrease of the maximum shear stress occurs with increasing the size of the nanotubes. Increasing the number of the wall layers of the nanotubes will cause (1) the decrease of the Young's modulus of the nanotubes; (2) the increase of the effective cross sectional area and (3) thus increase the total contact surface area at the bond interface and the allowable pullout force of the nanotube/polymer system. The allowable tensile stress of aligned nanotube/polymer composites could also be estimated by using Eq.(13). Although the author has previously addressed that the MWNTs could not be effectively used as nano-reinforcements for nanotube/polymer composites due to the stress not being continuously transferred from the outer to inner layers [32], for a structural stiffness point of view, the use of the MWNTs may have an advantage of avoiding debonding at the bond interface between the nanotubes and matrix of the composites. In some cases, the Young's modulus of the MWNTs is high enough for the design of advanced nanotube/polymer composites even if is comparatively smaller than that of the SWNTs.

In the present study, only analytical solutions are shown. The results are agreed with the solutions shown in other literatures for fibre pullout and fragmentation problem. Practically, the experimental investigation on a single nanotube pullout test is hardly conducted. The current work can provide basic information to describe the stress transfer mechanism of the nanotube/polymer composites that have not been previously discussed elsewhere.

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Appendix I

$$A_1 = \frac{\alpha(1-2k\nu_{NT}) + \gamma(1-2k\nu_m)}{U_2 - 2kU_1} \quad (\text{A1})$$

$$A_2 = \frac{-\gamma(1-2k\nu_m)}{U_2 - 2kU_1} \quad (\text{A2})$$

$$U_1 = \frac{\gamma}{8} \left\{ 2\eta_1 b^2 \ln\left(\frac{b}{R_{NT}}\right) \left[1 + \gamma \left(\frac{b^2}{R_{NT}^2} + 1 \right) \right] - 2\eta_2 (b^2 + R_{NT}^2) + 4b^2 - 2\eta_1 (b^2 - R_{NT}^2) \right\} \quad (\text{A3})$$

$$U_2 = \frac{\nu_m \gamma}{4} \left\{ 2\eta_1 b^2 \ln\left(\frac{b}{R_{NT}}\right) (1 + \gamma) - \eta_2 (b^2 + R_{NT}^2) + 2b^2 - \eta_1 (b^2 - R_{NT}^2) \right\} \quad (\text{A4})$$

$$k = \frac{\alpha\nu_{NT} + \gamma\nu_m}{\alpha(1-\nu_{NT}) + 1 + 2\gamma + \nu_m} \quad (\text{A5})$$

$$\alpha = \frac{E_{NT}}{E_m} \quad (\text{A6})$$

$$\eta_1 = \frac{2(1+\nu_m)}{\nu_m} \quad (\text{A7})$$

$$\eta_2 = \frac{1+2\nu_m}{\nu_m} \quad (\text{A8})$$

$$\lambda = \sqrt{A_1} \quad (\text{A9})$$

$$\omega_1 = \frac{\frac{A_2}{A_1} - \left(1 + \frac{A_2}{A_1} \right) \cosh(\lambda L)}{\sinh(\lambda L)} \sigma_{pullout} \quad (\text{A10})$$

$$\omega_2 = \left(1 + \frac{A_2}{A_1} \right) \sigma_{pullout} \quad (\text{A11})$$